

Experiences and recollections with Generative AI in Introductory Programming: A Case Study

Montse Farreras¹

¹ Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, UPCBarcelonaTech, Barcelona, Spain

Email: montserrat.farreras@upc.edu

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15874232>

Abstract

GenAI is here to stay, making it essential to prepare and support students in its effective use. Like most innovations, it brings both opportunities and challenges. GenAI has quickly become a versatile tool across domains—from creative writing to complex problem-solving—with programming emerging as one of its most transformative applications. These models offer not only code solutions and inspiration but also instant, iterative feedback, positioning them as powerful tools for skill development. This paper aims to review current literature and present a case study on the use of GenAI in an introductory programming course, assessing whether and how GenAI should support learning. We share findings and propose strategies for integrating these tools into educational settings while preserving the depth and integrity of student learning.

Keywords: Active Learning; Engineering Education; Artificial Intelligence; Project Approaches.

1 Introduction

The emergence and rapid proliferation of Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI), particularly Large Language Models (LLMs), mark a significant technological inflection point with profound implications across numerous sectors. As AI technologies continue to evolve and permeate various aspects of engineering practice, there is a growing need to reassess and adapt traditional educational paradigms to prepare future engineers for an AI-driven world.

Generative AI (GenAI) refers to a class of artificial intelligence models capable of producing text, code, images, and other forms of media in response to user prompts. Tools like OpenAI's ChatGPT⁴, Google's Gemini⁵, DeepSeek⁶ and GitHub Copilot⁷ are trained on extensive datasets and are able to generate highly coherent, human-like outputs. These capabilities make GenAI valuable for a wide range of tasks, including content creation, problem-solving, and decision-making. By enabling users to quickly draft documents, improve written work, and access information effortlessly, these tools are reshaping productivity and how we work and learn.

In educational settings, GenAI functions as an endlessly patient and always-available tutor. It delivers explanations adapted to individual learners' levels, assists in brainstorming, and offers real-time feedback—supporting a highly personalized and self-directed learning experience. Therefore, in recent years, GenAI tools are being explored for their potential to enhance learning environments, foster innovation, and prepare students for a digitally transformed future. (Dwivedi et al., 2021; Su & Yang, (2023); Noroozi et al. (2024)).

In engineering education, students have quickly embraced GenAI tools, especially those geared toward programming (Becker (2023)). Introductory programming courses, often serving as foundational pillars within engineering and computer science curricula, find themselves at the epicenter of this technological disruption.

⁴ <https://chat.openai.com>

⁵ <https://gemini.google.com>

⁶ <https://chat.deepseek.com/>

⁷ <https://github.com/features/copilot>

GenAI models exhibit striking proficiency in tasks central to these courses, including generating syntactically and logically plausible code solutions that can rival student performance, explaining complex programming concepts and code snippets, significantly enhancing the clarity and helpfulness of compiler error messages, and even simulating interactions akin to human tutors or teaching assistants. These tools are transforming how students engage with programming, often surpassing traditional methods that rely on static documentation, textbooks, or delayed instructor feedback (Yilmaz et al. (2023)).

The research community views GenAI as a potentially transformative force in education (Alasadi & Baiz (2023)), offering solutions to challenges like scalability and personalized feedback. However, ChatGPT, a cutting-edge natural language processing (NLP) model developed by OpenAI in 2019 (Lund & Wang, (2023)) was only released in late 2022. We are still in the early stages of understanding how to effectively integrate them into academic settings. Questions remain around when, how, and to what extent these tools should be incorporated into coursework and curricula and research around the topic has grown exponentially in the last years (Qadir (2023); Giannakos et al. (2024)).

In this context, this paper examines the capabilities and challenges of GenAI in a Python Introductory Programming Seminar, with the objective to assess whether and how GenAI should support learning. The methodology includes a narrative literature review and a case study. Specifically, the paper makes the following contributions:

- A state-of-the-art academic literature review of GenAI adoption and application into introductory programming education; identifying emerging pedagogical trends and adaptations, and key opportunities and challenges highlighted by researchers and educators.
- A case study analyzing students' experiences with GenAI, evaluating feedback and performance outcomes.
- An assessment of GenAI's impact on learning, aligned with Bofill's (2022) five-phase framework (motivation, information retrieval, understanding, practice, and feedback).
- Best practice guidelines and future research directions to accompany GenAI integration in programming educational settings.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents a comprehensive overview of the documented landscape regarding GenAI adoption into introductory programming education; This review establishes a crucial context for the subsequent case study; section 3 presents the GenAI assisted Python programming seminar; section 4 evaluates the seminar outcome; section 5 presents an assessment of GenAI's impact on learning and provides a best practices guidelines; concluding remarks are written in section 6.

2 The Current Landscape of GenAI in Introductory Programming Education

The period following the public release of powerful GenAI tools like ChatGPT in late 2022 has been characterized by rapid and widespread adoption, particularly among students. It has been necessary to understand these tools and explore their potential to build an *"Innovative pathway: Bridging Professional Development and Active learning"* (conference topic) to prepare students for a digitally transformed future.

Research indicates a high uptake of these tools in educational settings, specially in introductory programming courses (Becker et al (2023)). Surveys and usage tracking studies reveal that a significant proportion of students utilize GenAI for their academic work, sometimes irrespective of whether these tools are formally integrated into the course structure by instructors (Prather et al (2024)). Student perception surveys often report that AI systems are found helpful for academic tasks, although students also demonstrate awareness of the technology's limitations (Keuning et al (2024)) . However, usage patterns exhibit considerable variability.

Observational studies and analyses of interaction logs show that student engagement ranges from seeking occasional clarification or debugging assistance to heavy reliance on GenAI for generating entire solutions (Kazemitabaar et al (2023)).

The toolbox available to students and educators is diverse and expanding rapidly. General-purpose LLMs, most notably OpenAI's ChatGPT¹, remain widely used due to their accessibility and broad capabilities. Code-specific assistants integrated into development environments, such as GitHub Copilot⁴, are also prevalent, offering real-time code suggestions and completion. Increasingly, other powerful models like Google's Gemini² and Anthropic's Claude⁸ are entering the landscape, each with slightly different strengths and interfaces.

Within the specific context of introductory programming education, the literature highlights several dominant applications of these GenAI tools (Denny et. AI (2024)):

- **Code Generation/Completion:** Generating code from descriptions, from snippets to full solutions.
- **Code Explanation/Comprehension:** Understanding code snippets, logic, or concepts.
- **Debugging/Error Message Enhancement:** Identifying errors and translating cryptic compiler messages.
- **Tutoring/Help-Seeking:** Providing on-demand, interactive assistance 24/7, like a personalized TA.
- **Broader Learning Support:** Understanding assignments, finding APIs, generating practice exercises, exploring alternatives.

Case studies illustrate these uses: Specialized tutors like RAGMan (Ma et al (2024)) and CS-Discuss (Yoonseok (2025)) use techniques like Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) and guardrails for tailored, safe guidance, reporting positive student feedback and engagement. Other examples include chatbots for domain-specific activities, specific simulations (Liang (2023)) and practice environments like Codecademy's simulators (Hashmi et al (2024)). Observational studies reveal diverse interaction patterns, including concerning ones like submitting entire problems to AI without prior effort and infrequent verification of AI solutions (Amoozadeh (2024)). Comparative studies show mixed results on learning outcomes, with some reporting increased interest (Alpizar (2025), Llerena et al (2024)) and others finding no significant performance difference but reduced use of traditional resources (Yuankai et al (2024)).

The focus in computing education is shifting from debating GenAI's permissibility to developing strategies for safe and effective integration that supports learning. There's a noticeable trend from using general tools towards developing specialized educational AI systems with pedagogical safeguards (Vidalis et al (2024)) and to personalized and adaptive learning tailoring content, difficulty, and feedback at scale (Onyebuchi et al (2025)). While, another trend gears towards is explicitly teaching AI collaboration skills (Denny et al (2024)).

2.1 The Research Perspective: promises and pitfalls of GenAI

Integrating GenAI into introductory programming education presents substantial opportunities, including personalized learning at scale, increased engagement, and 24/7 support that enhances accessibility - especially in large classes. It boosts student motivation, autonomy, and confidence while preparing them for the AI-driven workforce. Additionally, it enables students to progress more quickly and tackle complex challenges earlier. However, if not carefully guided, the ease of assistance could undermine deep learning by minimizing the productive struggle essential for long-term understanding (Yilmaz et al, 2023; Prather, 2024; Alasadi & Baiz, 2023).

While AI can greatly enhance productivity, some educators express significant concerns sometimes viewing the technology with caution or skepticism (Mittal et al. (2024); Sharples (2023)). Notably the risk of over-reliance

⁸ <https://claude.ai/>

that can hinder skill development and negatively impact learning, particularly among lower-performing students. It also raises concerns about academic integrity, as AI-generated code complicates assessment validity in unsupervised settings. Ethical issues include bias in AI outputs, unequal access, privacy risks, lack of transparency, and intellectual property concerns.

Moreover, practical barriers such as AI inaccuracy, infrastructure costs, faculty training needs, and curriculum redesign further complicate implementation. These challenges are deeply interconnected, requiring a holistic approach that combines thoughtful assessment reform and pedagogical innovation.

3 The AI-assisted Python Programming Seminar

We studied the impact of GenAI usage in a 20-hour introductory Python course aimed at students with prior experience in languages like C or Java. The course followed a problem-based, game-driven approach rather than traditional lectures. Its core was an escape room game where students solved programming challenges (e.g., Morse decoder, turtle graphics, number converters) to unlock clues, blending fun with serious learning. Game elements enhanced motivation, while embedded hints in the course notes encouraged engagement with the material. The escape room covered 10 hours; the remaining time focused on team-based programming projects to foster collaboration and practical application (Bofill 2022).

In this edition, students were directed to recommended IDEs and GenAI tools for development. The course, along with supporting materials and usage guidelines for GenAI, was structured as follows:

1. **To start:** Students were introduced to the course and asked to complete a questionnaire to set expectations and reflect on their current AI tool usage. They received Python notebooks with simple code examples to illustrate syntax, using Google Colab for experimentation. ChatGPT was recommended for clarifying explanations and deepening understanding.
2. **To continue- The escape room:** A escape room was designed to maintain challenge and avoid trivialization, emphasizing that the game's goal was learning (Bofill 2022). Challenges included a Morse decoder, a recursive Hanoi Tower visual using turtle graphics, a hex-to-decimal converter, and a system-of-equations solver using the Gauss-Jordan method. Templates were provided to guide students in Object-Oriented Programming and to limit overreliance on GenAI by requiring students to understand and adapt code, rather than copying it blindly.
3. For students already familiar with programming, mastering Python syntax is relatively easy (learning phase 3 (Bofill (2022))). The real challenge lies in applying this knowledge to problem-solving (learning phase 4). A passive, lecture-based approach to teaching syntax would be unengaging. Since programming is a skill, it must be developed through practice.
4. **To live- The personal project:** In this part of the course the students are asked to work on a project of their own interest and they are encouraged to use AI freely as they like for brainstorming, developing and debugging.
5. **To rest:** At the course's end, students completed a feedback questionnaire reflecting on their learning outcomes, the course experience, and their use of GenAI throughout.

4 AI-Assisted Course Evaluation

To evaluate the activity and enhance future editions, we developed a questionnaire based on the standardized Student Evaluation of Educational Quality (SEEQ) instrument, which includes both closed and open-ended questions. Table 1 presents the questions specifically related to the use of GenAI. Students were asked to complete two questionnaires: one before the course and another after its completion. The first two questions in Table 1 (italicized) address GenAI usage prior to the seminar, while the remaining questions were answered afterward.

Table 1. Summary of the questionnaire based on SEEQ regarding the use of GenAI tools

	Statement	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
1	I usually use GenAI for my studies	1	2	3	4	5
2	For what purpose do you use GenAI in your studies?	For all I can	To solve the assignments	For programming	To study (feedback)	I do not use it
3	For this seminar: the use of GenAI tools has helped me to solve the challenges	1	2	3	4	5
4	The use of GenAI has helped me to acquire a deeper level of understanding	1	2	3	4	5
5	Using GenAI increases my motivation because I make faster progress and do not get stuck	1	2	3	4	5
6	Besides the seminar documentation what other sources have you used?	GenAI	Official libraries documentation	Youtube videos	Google	Others
7	Explain your experience using the GenAI tools					
8	What is your favorite GenAI?					

4.1 Questionnaire results analysis

This section analyzes the results based on the students answers to the questionnaire.

Regarding the two preliminary questions about GenAI use: Question: "I usually use GenAI for my studies" was answered with a unanimous "Strongly agree" and Figure 1 left shows the distribution of purposes (answering question 2). Figure 1 right shows the favorite GenAI tool obtained compiling results from question 8.

Figure 1. Feedback display on the GenAI purpose (left) and favorite model (right)

To add value to the GenAI assessment, GenAI tools have been used here to analyze the results presented in Figure 1. When prompted with the Figure ChatGPT answer: "Looking at both charts in Figure 1 together reveals a clear picture of GenAI usage among students. The data shows that while GenAI is used across multiple academic activities, it's predominantly leveraged for study feedback (38%) and programming assistance (29%), with fewer students using it for assignments (14%) or as an all-purpose tool (19%). This usage pattern aligns with their tool preferences, where ChatGPT (33%) and DeepSeek (29%) together capture the majority of user preference, followed by the programming-specific GitHub Copilot (24%)"⁹

⁹ In this analysis, an interesting observation emerged: while ChatGPT provided the correct answer, the Claude model confused itself (Claude) with DeepSeek, incorrectly stating that Claude was one of the students' preferred tools

Figure 2. Feedback display on the GenAI usability during the seminar.

The data in Figure 2 (coming from questions 3,4,5) shows very positive reception overall, with the strongest positive impact being on motivation, followed by deeper understanding and then problem-solving.

Figure 3 reflects students answers to questions 6 and 7. Overall, Figure 3 charts reveal that participants heavily relied on internet resources and specifically GenAI tools for documentation, with official documentation used much less frequently. For GenAI applications specifically, explanation capabilities were most highly valued, followed by search functionality and brainstorming assistance. This suggests GenAI is particularly effective as an educational tool that helps participants understand concepts rather than just as a practical coding utility (Claude Generated).

Figure 3. Feedback display on documentation sources (left) and usability of GenAI models to carry on with the Python programming seminar (right).

4.2 Further analysis based on students' feedback and performance

Based on selected comments from students regarding their experience with GenAI tools, they showed awareness of GenAI limitations in terms of accuracy, reliability and potential "hallucinations" (generating incorrect or false information). In their words: *"For small examples it was good but not for bigger programs,"*; *"Useful, but you need to know how to use it."* or *"It does not solve your problems but it helps"*. They particularly appreciated its help with syntax correction, code snippets, and identifying the right libraries: *"Python has a lot of libraries—ChatGPT helped me quickly find the one I needed and how to use it."*

Others described GenAI as a patient tutor that provides timely feedback and explanations: *"It helped me a lot to understand code snippets and the language itself."*

Considering students' performance, a notable outcome of introducing GenAI into the Python programming seminar was the increased complexity of the personal projects chosen by students. A qualitative comparison reveals that, in this edition of the course (where the use of GenAI tools was encouraged), students opted for more ambitious projects—for example, a music media player, a chatbot with LLMs that plays musical notes and chords, a role-playing game, a tool to plot real-time sensor temperature, a plant recognition model, a turtle-based drawing app etc...

This contrasts with the previous year, when students—without GenAI support—tended to choose simpler projects suggested by the instructor, such as card games, a snake game, a basic drawing program limited to circles, a simple encryption algorithm, or a to-do list app.

These results highlight both an increase in student motivation and the productivity gains enabled by GenAI tools. At the same time there is a recognition of risks and limitations.

4.3 One more experiment

GenAI tools are proving to be extremely effective as code assistants—but where is the limit? These tools can solve complete assignments from an introductory Python programming course. For example, GitHub Copilot successfully completed the Tower of Hanoi problem—a classic recursion exercise—by interpreting the comments within a provided code template, generating functional code, and even animating the solution using Turtle graphics.

To further explore the tool's capabilities, we tried a more ambitious prompt: *"Please write me a program with similar functionality to Microsoft Word."* The response was: *"Creating a full-featured word processor like Microsoft Word is an enormous task—Microsoft Word is the result of decades of development, with thousands of features including rich text formatting, (...). But I can absolutely help you build a simplified version (...). Here's a basic rich text editor in Python using tkinter: (...)"*

After providing the initial code and explanations, the tool continued: *"What new features would you like to add—support for images, spellcheck...? I can expand the version step by step for you!"*

In theory, with enough patience and iterative prompting, one could gradually reach the original goal. In practice, however, the process might be more time-consuming and frustrating than simply coding it from scratch.

5 Recollections and guidelines

GenAI is no longer a future prospect but a present reality. Its integration into educational settings is essential for workforce preparation and AI literacy, equipping students with industry-relevant skills. Based on the observations in our Case Study, we present an assessment of GenAI's impact on learning, aligned with Bofill's (2022) five-phase framework ((1)motivation, (2)information retrieval, (3)understanding, (4)practice, and (5)feedback). The following benefits have been identified:

1. Increased student engagement and motivation, necessary precursor to any learning (phase 1).
2. Enhanced self-efficacy, contributing to deeper understanding and accelerated learning (phases 4 and 5).
3. Improved information access, with students effectively using GenAI as an intelligent search engine (phase 2).

4. Appreciation for 24/7 AI tutoring (phase 3), offering personalized and timely feedback, supporting phases 4 and 5 by making learning more interactive and reducing frustration while promoting autonomy and confidence.

Overall, we conclude that GenAI effectively supported all stages of the learning process: motivation, information retrieval, understanding, application, and validation; enhancing students learning.

Concerns regarding GenAI's reliability and potential for "hallucinations" can be mitigated through appropriate usage. Best practice strategies may include:

1. Raising student awareness of risks and limitations (in this course, students quickly identified them);
2. Gradually integrating GenAI with prompt iteration and continuous frequent testing;
3. Verifying AI-generated content against official documentation;
4. Using GenAI as a collaborative assistant rather than a source of final answers;
5. Reinforcing foundational knowledge through manual coding practice.

Institutional barriers must first be addressed through instructor training and the development of best practice guidelines for effective GenAI use. These practices should then be communicated to students to ensure meaningful integration.

Finally, academic integrity and assessment validity—highlighted in the literature—call for assessment reform that should shift responsibility for learning back to students, grounded in the trust that they are intrinsically motivated to learn. Ethical considerations surrounding GenAI, while significant, are beyond the scope of this paper.

6 Conclusions

GenAI is here to stay, making it essential to prepare and support students in its effective use. Like most innovations, it presents both opportunities and challenges.

The benefits are well documented: enhanced personalized learning, prompt feedback, improved information accessibility, and increased student engagement, motivation, self-efficacy, and autonomy. Moreover, these advantages scale across large student cohorts and offer significant potential for accelerated learning and deeper understanding by supporting a highly personalized and self-directed learning experience.

To tackle the challenges, it is crucial to first overcome implementation barriers by training instructors, redesigning curricula, establishing and disseminating best practice guidelines, and reforming assessment methods to restore the responsibility of learning to students.

Beyond education, GenAI's greatest practical utility as a coding assistant may lie in its function as an intelligent search engine—guiding users toward relevant libraries or solution strategies and thereby improving productivity.

A widespread concern involves long-term over-reliance on AI tools, potentially undermining fundamental learning. However, this can be mitigated by recognizing that we are entering a new era of programming. Looking ahead, two scenarios may unfold: in one, we design and develop software using natural language through iterative prompting, potentially lagging behind traditional coding in efficiency; in the other, the inherent imprecision of natural language may reaffirm the need for formal code, leading us back to current practices.

References

- Alasadi, Eman A., Baiz, Carlos R. (2023) Generative AI in Education and Research: Opportunities, Concerns, and Solutions, *Journal of Chemical Education*, American Chemical Society, 2965-2971.
- Alpizar-Chacon, Isaac & Keuning, Hieke. (2025). Student's Use of Generative AI as a Support Tool in an Advanced Web Development Course. doi:10.48550/arXiv.2503.15684.
- Amoozadeh, M., Nam, D., Prol, D., Alfageeh, A., Prather, J., Hilton, M., Ragavan, S. S., & Alipour, M. A. (2024). Student-AI Interaction: A Case Study of CS1 students. *Koli Calling International Conference on Computing Education Research*, 1–13.
- Aydin Ö., Karaarslan E. (2022). OpenAI ChatGPT generated literature review: Digital twin in healthcare. *Emerging Computer Technologies 2*. 10.2139/ssrn.4308687
- Baidoo-Anu D., Owusu Ansah L. (2023). Education in the era of generative artificial intelligence (AI): Understanding the potential benefits of ChatGPT in promoting teaching and learning. *Journal of AI*. 7. Doi:10.61969/jai.1337500..
- Becker, B. A., Craig, M., Denny, P., Keuning, H., Kiesler, N., Leinonen, J. & Quille, K. (2023). Generative ai in introductory programming. *Computer Science Curricula*.
- Bofill P., Farreras M., Armengol J. (2022) An Escape Room for Learning Computer Programming. *PAEE/ALE 2022 Conference*
- Denny, Paul and Leinonen, Juho and Prather, James and Luxton-Reilly, Andrew and Amarouche, Thezyrie and Becker, Brett A. and Reeves, Brent N. (2024) Prompt Problems: A New Programming Exercise for the Generative AI Era. *Association for Computing Machinery*
- Denny, P., Prather, J., Becker, B. A., Finnie-Ansley, J., Hellas, A., Leinonen, J., Luxton-Reilly, A., Reeves, B. N., Santos, E. A., Sarsa, S., Sato, D., Kazemitabaar, M., Craig, M., Keuning, H., Kiesler, N., Malmi, L., Quille, K., Ragavan, S. S., Tan, L., ... Weintrop, D. (2024). Beyond the Hype: A Comprehensive Review of Trends, Tools, Challenges, and Opportunities for Generative AI in Introductory Programming Education. *Working Group Reports on Innovation and Technology in Computer Science Education (ITiCSE-WGR)*
- Dwivedi Y. K., Hughes L., Ismagilova E., Aarts G., Coombs C., Crick T., Williams M. D. (2021). Artificial intelligence (AI): Multidisciplinary perspectives on emerging challenges, opportunities, and agenda for research, practice, and policy. *International Journal of Information Management*
- Hashmi N., Li Z., Parise S., Shankaranarayanan G., (2024) Generative AI's impact on programming students: frustration and confidence across learning styles. *Issues in Information Systems* V.25 I 3 p 371-385, 2024.
- J. Qadir, (2023) Engineering Education in the Era of ChatGPT: Promise and Pitfalls of Generative AI for Education. *IEEE Global Engineering Education Conference (EDUCON)*, Kuwait, Kuwait, 2023, pp. 1-9
- Kazemitabaar, M., Chow, J., Ma, C. K. T., Ericson, B. J., Weintrop, D., & Grossman, T. (2023). Studying the effect of AI Code Generators on Supporting Novice Learners in Introductory Programming. *CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. 1–23
- Keuning, H., Denny, P., Luxton-Reilly, A., Prather, J., Becker, B. A., Reeves, B. N., & Sarsa, S. (2024). Students' Perceptions and Use of Generative AI Tools for Programming Across Different Computing Courses. 10.48550/arXiv.2410.06865.
- U. Mittal, S. Sai, V. Chamola and D. Sangwan, A Comprehensive Review on Generative AI for Education. *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 142733-142759, 2024
- Giannakos, M., Azevedo, R., Brusilovsky, P., Cukurova, M., Dimitriadis, Y., Hernandez-Leo, D., Rienties, B. (2024). The promise and challenges of generative AI in education. *Behaviour & Information Technology*, 1–27.
- Llerena-Izquierdo, Joe, Mendez-Reyes, Johan, Ayala-Carabaja, Raquel, Andrade-Martinez, Cesar (2024) Innovations in Introductory Programming Education: The Role of AI with Google Colab and Gemini. *Education Sciences* 2024 v.14 - 12 p.2227-7102
- Liang, J. T., Yang, C., & Myers, B. A. (2023). A Large-Scale Survey on the Usability of AI Programming Assistants: Successes and Challenges. *Association for Computing Machinery* 2024 10.1145/3597503.3608128.
- Lund, B.D. and Wang, T. (2023), Chatting about ChatGPT: how may AI and GPT impact academia and libraries? *Library Hi Tech News*, Vol. 40 No. 3, pp. 26-29
- Ma, I., Krone-Martins, A., & Lopes, C. (2024). Integrating AI Tutors in a Programming Course. *SIGCSE 2024 Virtual Conference*
- Noroozi, O., Soleimani, S., Farrokhnia, M., & Banihashem, S.K. (2024). Generative AI in education: Pedagogical, theoretical, and methodological perspectives. *International Journal of Technology in Education (IJTE)*, 7(3), 373-385
- Onyebuchi, Nneamaka & Olusola, Ayeni & Hamad, Nancy & Osawaru, Blessing & Adewusi, Ololade. (2024). AI in education: A review of personalized learning and educational technology. *GSC Advanced Research and Reviews*. 18. 261-271. Doi:10.30574/gscarr.2024.18.2.0062.
- Prather, J., Denny, P., Leinonen, J., Becker, B. A., Albluwi, I., Craig, M., Keuning, H., Kiesler, N., Luxton-Reilly, A., MacNeil, S., Petersen, A., Reeves, B. N., Sarsa, S., & Zingaro, D. (2024). The Widening Gap: The Benefits and Harms of Generative AI for Novice Programmers. *ACM Conference on International Computing Education Research-Volume 1*, 469–486.
- Sharples, M. (2023). Towards social generative AI for education: theory, practices and ethics. *Learning: Research and Practice*, 9(2), 159–167.
- Su, J., & Yang, W. (2023). Unlocking the Power of ChatGPT: A Framework for Applying Generative AI in Education. *ECNU Review of Education*, 6(3), 355-366.
- Vidalis, Sofia & Subramanian, Rajarajan & Najafi, Fazil. (2024). Revolutionizing Engineering Education: The Impact of AI Tools on Student Learning. *2024 ASEE Annual Conference & Exposition*. Doi:10.18260/1-2--47950.
- Yilmaz, R., Karaoglan Y., Fatma G. (2023) The effect of generative artificial intelligence (AI)-based tool use on students' computational thinking skills, programming self-efficacy and motivation. *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence* 4, 100147
- Yoonseok Yang, Jack Liu, J.D. Zamfirescu-Pereira, John DeNero (2025) Scalable Small-Group CS Tutoring System with AI. *56th ACM Technical Symposium on Computer Science Education (SIGCSE TS 2025)*
- Yuankai Xue, Hanlin Chen, Gina R. Bai, Robert Tairas, and Yu Huang. (2024). Does ChatGPT Help With Introductory Programming? An Experiment of Students Using ChatGPT in CS1. *International Conference on Software Engineering: Software Engineering Education and Training (ICSE-SEET '24)*